

Participant Information

Full name:

Gender: Age:

Full Address (including city/village & district name):

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GPS Coordinates of location:

Education level:

Phone Number:

Email Address:

Informed Consent Form

Project title: Assessing the Impact and Management Status of Parthenium Weed (*Parthenium hysterophorus* L.) in Dhofar, Oman

I agree to be involved in the above research project as a respondent. I have read the relevant research information sheet and understand the nature of the research and my role in it.

I would / would not like my name acknowledged in the acknowledgments page of reports.

.....
Signature of the research subject/respondent

Date:

Assessing the Impact and Management Status of Parthenium Weed (*Parthenium hysterophorus* L.) in Dhofar, Oman

Respondent No:

Section A: Awareness

A1. Have you heard about parthenium weed?

1. Yes 2. No

Don't ask further questions if answer to A1 is No.

A2. If yes, can you identify parthenium weed? (Show a sample of the plant to the respondent)

1. Yes 2. No

A3. Do you think it is a weed/unwanted plant?

1. Yes 2. No 3. Do not know

A4. What do you call this plant locally? (Write the name provided by the respondent below in Arabic)

A5. At which growth stage can you recognize plants of parthenium weed?

1. Seedling 2. Rosette 3. Flowering 4. Maturity

A6. Can you identify parthenium weed seed?

1. Yes 2. No

A7. When did you first see parthenium weed?

_____ Years ago

A8. Did you seek any information about parthenium weed or its control from fellow farmers, extension workers etc.?

1. Yes 2. No

A9. Currently, where can you find parthenium weed?

	Location	Yes/No	When did you first see it in this area?
1	Around the house	1. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes 2. <input type="checkbox"/> No	_____ Years ago
2	Flower/Vegetable Gardens	1. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes 2. <input type="checkbox"/> No	_____ Years ago
3	Crop/Farm lands	1. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes 2. <input type="checkbox"/> No	_____ Years ago
4	Rangelands/Grazing lands	1. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes 2. <input type="checkbox"/> No	_____ Years ago
5	Natural forests	1. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes 2. <input type="checkbox"/> No	_____ Years ago
6	Along the roads	1. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes 2. <input type="checkbox"/> No	_____ Years ago
7	Wadies	1. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes 2. <input type="checkbox"/> No	_____ Years ago
8	Irrigation water channels	1. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes 2. <input type="checkbox"/> No	_____ Years ago
9	Waste lands	1. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes 2. <input type="checkbox"/> No	_____ Years ago
10	Other (specify)	1. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes 2. <input type="checkbox"/> No	_____ Years ago

A10. Which season do you see it often?

1. Summer 2. Winter 3. Spring 4. Autumn 5. Throughout the year

A11. How do you think it was introduced in your area/farm through?

1. Wind 2. Irrigation water 3. Animal movement
 4. Contaminated crop seed 5. Contaminated farm machinery
 6. Flower bouquet 7. Do not know

A12. Have you seen its seeds in crop seed lots, on farm machinery or in animal feed?

1. Yes (If yes, specify where) 2. No

Section B: Impact on Agricultural Production

Crops

B1. Please indicate whether the following crops have been infested by parthenium weed on your farm.

If answer in 4th and 5th is "1. Not infested" don't ask question in 6th column

	Name of crop	Do you grow this crop	Prevalence of parthenium weed this year* 1. Not Infested 2. Light/low 3. Medium/moderate 4. Heavy/high	Prevalence of parthenium weed in last year 1. Not Infested 2. Light/low 3. Medium/moderate 4. Heavy/high	When did you first see parthenium weed in this crop? (Years ago)
1	Wheat	1. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes 2. <input type="checkbox"/> No			
2	Barseem	1. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes 2. <input type="checkbox"/> No			
3	Corn	1. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes 2. <input type="checkbox"/> No			
4		1. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes 2. <input type="checkbox"/> No			
5		1. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes 2. <input type="checkbox"/> No			
6		1. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes 2. <input type="checkbox"/> No			
7	Vegetables (specify below) 1. _____ 2. _____ 3. _____ 4. _____ 5. _____				
8	Fruits (specify below) 1. _____ 2. _____ 3. _____ 4. _____ 5. _____				
9	Other crops (specify below) 1. _____ 2. _____ 3. _____ 4. _____ 5. _____				

*1. Not Infested, 2. Light: 1 Plant per square meter; 3. Medium: 2 Plants per square meter; 4. Heavy: 3 or more plants per square meter

B2. What is true for total area infested by parthenium weed at your farm during the last 5 years?

1. Stayed same 2. Increased 3. Decreased

B3. What is true for the density of parthenium weed at your farm during the last 5 years?

1. Stayed same 2. Increased 3. Decreased

B4. Please indicate the area and average yield of following crops at your farm.

Please note answers in units specified below, if the answers are in different units e.g. acre / mounds per acre etc., convert them or mention below clearly

	Name of crop	Area (ha)	Average yield last year (kg/ha)	Average yield year before last year (kg/ha)	In your opinion, yield loss due to parthenium weed (kg/ha or %)
1	What				
2	Barseem				
3	Corn				
4					
5					
6					
7	Vegetables (specify below) 1. _____ 2. _____ 3. _____ 4. _____ 5. _____				
8	Fruits (specify below) 1. _____ 2. _____ 3. _____ 4. _____ 5. _____				
9	Other crops (specify below) 1. _____ 2. _____ 3. _____ 4. _____ 5. _____				

B5. Please specify different management strategies you have adopted and/or adopting to control parthenium weed in your cropping area.

Name of crop	Have you implemented any management strategy to control parthenium?	If yes, what management approaches have you adopted?	Please indicate the estimated time which you require for each of these activities (hrs/day)	Please indicate what additional costs are associated with these management activities (excluding your labour costs)
Wheat	1. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes 2. <input type="checkbox"/> No	1. <input type="checkbox"/> Weeding*		
		2. <input type="checkbox"/> Herbicides		
		If herbicide, its name _____		
		3. <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify) _____		
Barseem	1. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes 2. <input type="checkbox"/> No	1. <input type="checkbox"/> Weeding		
		2. <input type="checkbox"/> Herbicides		
		If herbicide, its name _____		
		3. <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify) _____		
Corn	1. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes 2. <input type="checkbox"/> No	1. <input type="checkbox"/> Weeding		
		2. <input type="checkbox"/> Herbicides		
		If herbicide, its name _____		
		3. <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify) _____		
	1. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes 2. <input type="checkbox"/> No	1. <input type="checkbox"/> Weeding		
		2. <input type="checkbox"/> Herbicides		
		If herbicide, its name _____		
		3. <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify) _____		
	1. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes 2. <input type="checkbox"/> No	1. <input type="checkbox"/> Weeding		
		2. <input type="checkbox"/> Herbicides		
		If herbicide, its name _____		
		3. <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify) _____		

	1. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes 2. <input type="checkbox"/> No	1. <input type="checkbox"/> Weeding 2. <input type="checkbox"/> Herbicides If herbicide, its name _____ 3. <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify) _____		
Vegetables (specify below) 1. _____ 2. _____ 3. _____ 4. _____ 5. _____	1. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes 2. <input type="checkbox"/> No	1. <input type="checkbox"/> Weeding 2. <input type="checkbox"/> Herbicides If herbicide, its name and crop in which it is used _____ _____ _____ 3. <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify) _____		
Fruits (specify below) 1. _____ 2. _____ 3. _____ 4. _____ 5. _____	1. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes 2. <input type="checkbox"/> No	1. <input type="checkbox"/> Weeding 2. <input type="checkbox"/> Herbicides If herbicide, its name and crop in which it is used _____ _____ _____ 3. <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify) _____		
Other crops (specify below) 1. _____ 2. _____ 3. _____ 4. _____ 5. _____	1. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes 2. <input type="checkbox"/> No	1. <input type="checkbox"/> Weeding 2. <input type="checkbox"/> Herbicides If herbicide, its name and crop in which it is used _____ _____ _____ 3. <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify) _____		

*Weeding means uprooting or cutting manually.

Domestic Animals/Livestock

B6A. Do you have animals at your farm?

1. Yes 2. No

****If answer is "No", please don't ask further questions from B6B to C5.***

B6B. What type of animals do you have at your farm?

Animal	Total Number
Camel	
Sheep	
Cows	
Goats	
Chickens (Poultry)	
Other (Specify) _____ _____ _____	

B7. Do you collect fodder for any of your animals?

1. Yes 2. No

****If answer is "No", please skip questions B8 to B14***

B8. If Yes, please explain the source of your fodder collection.

1. Own land 2. Community land
3. Government land/forest 4. Other (Specify) _____

B9. Is parthenium weed infesting your fodder collection sites and/or fodder crops?

1. Yes 2. No 3. Do not know

B10. If yes, please explain the prevalence, area and density of parthenium weed in your fodder collection sites and/or fodder crops.

	Prevalence of Parthenium weed* 1. Light/low 2. Medium/moderate 3. Heavy/high	Area of infestation in last 5 years 1. Stayed the same 2. Increased 3. Decreased	Density of parthenium weed in last 5 years 1. Stayed the same 2. Increased 3. Decreased
1			
2			
3			

*1. Light: 1 Plant per square meter; 2. Medium: 2 Plants per square meter; 3. Heavy: 3 or more plants per square meter

B11. Has the prevalence of parthenium weed affected your ability to collect fodder?

1. Yes 2. No 3. Do not know

B12. If Yes, please explain how it has affected fodder collection?

	Effects on activities/operations	Yes/No	Total additional time taken (hrs/day)	Total extra cost (transport, wages per day etc.)
1	More time is required for fodder collection			
2	More careful collection methods are required to avoid personal contact with the plant	1. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes 2. <input type="checkbox"/> No		
3	Greater distances have to be travelled to collect from areas with less infestation	1. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes 2. <input type="checkbox"/> No		
4	Manual segregation of fodder from the weed	1. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes 2. <input type="checkbox"/> No		
5	Other (specify) _____	1. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes 2. <input type="checkbox"/> No		

B13. Do you think parthenium weed deteriorates the quality of fodder?

1. Yes 2. No

B14. If yes, how do you think it affects the fodder quality?

1. May cause toxicity 2. Reduce its palatability for livestock
3. Other (specify) _____

B15. Please indicate if you graze your animals?

1. Yes 2. No

****If answer is "No", please skip questions B16 to B22***

B16. Please provide details of the location where you graze them.

1. Own land 2. Community land/forest
 3. Government land/forest 4. Other (Specify) _____

B17. Is parthenium weed infesting your grazing land?

1. Yes 2. No 3. Do not know

B18. If yes, please explain the prevalence, area and density of parthenium weed

	Prevalence of Parthenium weed* 1. Light/low 2. Medium/moderate 3. Heavy/high	Area of infestation in the last 5 years 1. Stayed the same 2. Increased 3. Decreased	Density of parthenium weed in the last 5 years 1. Stayed the same 2. Increased 3. Decreased
1			
2			
3			

*1. Light: 1 Plant per square meter; 2. Medium: 2 Plants per square meter; 3. Heavy: 3 or more plants per square meter

B19. Has the prevalence of parthenium weed affected normal grazing routine of your animals?

1. Yes 2. No 3. Do not know

B20. If Yes, please explain how it has affected.

	More time required for grazing due to	Yes/No
1	Availability of less palatable fodder	1. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes 2. <input type="checkbox"/> No
2	Greater distances have to travel to graze on lands with relatively less infestation	1. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes 2. <input type="checkbox"/> No
3	Uprooting of parthenium from the grazing fields	1. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes 2. <input type="checkbox"/> No
4	Other (specify) _____	1. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes 2. <input type="checkbox"/> No

B21. Has the prevalence of parthenium weed also affected animal grazing behaviour and eating habits?

1. Yes

2. No

3. Do not know

Section C: Human and Animal Health Issues

Animal Health

C1. Do you think parthenium weed can affect animal health negatively?

1. Yes 2. No 3. Do not know

C2. Have any of your animals been affected by parthenium weed?

1. Yes 2. No 3. Do not know

**If answer is “yes”, please proceed further. In case of “No” and “Do not know” please skip questions C3 to C5*

C3. If yes, please provide details of the effects of parthenium on animals.

	Type of Animal Affected	Number of Animals Affected	Type of impact upon the animal: 1. skin allergy 2. breathing problems 3. loss of appetite 4. physical scars 5. reduced productivity 6. Other (specify)
1	Camel		
2	Sheep		
3	Cows		
4	Goats		
5	Chickens		
6	Other		

C4. Do you think that you have faced animal-related productivity losses due to parthenium weed infestation?

1. Yes 2. No 3. Do not know

C5. If yes, please mention what type of animal losses you had to face?

	Type of loss	Yes/No	Estimate of total associated costs
1	Death of an animal	1. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes 2. <input type="checkbox"/> No	
2	Increased Vet costs	1. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes 2. <input type="checkbox"/> No	
3	Reduced productivity (e.g. lower quantity or quality meat, milk, etc.)	1. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes 2. <input type="checkbox"/> No	
4	Other (Specify) _____	1. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes 2. <input type="checkbox"/> No	

Human Health

C6. Do you think parthenium weed can affect human health negatively?

1. Yes 2. No 3. Do not know

C7. Have you, your family member(s) or a friend experienced any parthenium induced health issues in the past year?

1. Yes 2. No 3. Do not know

**If answer is “yes”, please proceed further. In case of “No” and “Do not know” please skip questions C8*

C8. If yes, please provide details on the health issue

Person Affected	Description of the effect on health: 1. allergy 2. skin rashes or scars 3. breathing issues or asthma 4. Other (specify)	What activity resulted in the health issue? 1. weeding 2. fodder collection 3. firewood collection 4. Burning of woods during cooking 5. Other (specify below)	Estimated number of days lost per year due to illness	Time of Year/ Season when you are most affected	How many times the person was affected during last year	Method of treatment	Cost of treatment
Self							
Spouse							
Son							
Daughter							
Father							
Mother							
Other (Specify) _____							

Section D: Management in non-cropped areas

D1. What do you think about parthenium weed from a management point of view?

1. Very easy to manage 2. Easy to manage
3. Difficult to manage 4. Very difficult to manage 5. Do not know

D2. Do you think it should also be managed in non-cropped areas?

1. Yes 2. No 3. Do not know

D3. If yes, why do you think it is important to manage it in non-cropped areas (e.g. around your house, water channels, roadsides, pathways, play grounds etc.?)

1. To avoid infestation of cropped areas
2. To maintain plant community biodiversity
3. To avoid health problems
4. To reduce its further spread
5. All of the above

D4. Have you ever tried to control parthenium weed in non-cropped areas?

1. Yes 2. No

D5. If yes, which method did you use?

1. Manual removal 2. Mowing 3. Burning
4. Herbicide (specify) _____
5. Other (specify) _____

D6. Did you ever try to manage parthenium weed using a combination of two or more than two control methods?

1. Yes 2. No

D7. Do you know anything about “biological control” of parthenium weed?

1. Yes 2. No

D8. Have you ever observed a rodent, wild animal, farm animal, bird or insect eating parthenium weed plants/plant parts?

1. Yes 2. No

D9. If yes, please mention the name of animal and plant part

.....

D10. Has there been any discussion in the community regarding parthenium weed infestation and/or management?

1. Yes 2. No 3. Do not know

D11. If a management plan were to be devised for your region, would you be interested in participating?

Definitely Not	Not Likely	Do not know	Likely	Definitely Yes
<input type="checkbox"/>				

Section E: Uses of parthenium weed

E1. Please indicate if parthenium weed is used by your household for:

	Uses	Yes/No	Estimated total value/income per year
1	Medicinal Use	1. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes 2. <input type="checkbox"/> No If yes , for which disease or health problem 	
2	Soil Improvement/ Compost	1. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes 2. <input type="checkbox"/> No	
3	Livestock Feed	1. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes 2. <input type="checkbox"/> No	
4	Sale to people making flower bouquets	1. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes 2. <input type="checkbox"/> No	
5	To burn (as fuel for domestic purpose)	1. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes 2. <input type="checkbox"/> No	
6	Other (Building fences, household products etc.)	1. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes 2. <input type="checkbox"/> No	